

Effects of Carbon Fiber Strain and Resin Characteristics on Optimum Composite Performance

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ABSTRACT

This paper evaluates the recent improvements which have been achieved in continuous carbon fiber composite materials. The effects of increased fiber strengths (from 3 GPa to 4.5 GPa) on the experimental composite performance is reported. In addition, in order to isolate matrix contributions the behavior of composites containing three different matrix materials are compared. The resin matrix used as a control is Narmco 5208, a resin which is currently being used in numerous aerospace applications. Two other thermosetting resins with quite different chemical and mechanical characteristics were also evaluated. One of these systems, Narmco 5245, was recently developed to give increased toughness while the other is a high elongatin resin typically used for low viscosity wet winding. In addition to characterization of standard composite mechanical behavior, particular emphasis was placed on evaluation of the impact behavior of the 5208 and 5245 composite systems. Impact resistance was evaluated by measurement of both the total force required to penetrate composite panels and the amount of damage incurred during low energy impact events. The results of these evaluations indicate that considerable improvement in impact behavior is achieved with composites composed of high strength fiber and resin systems with increased toughness.

INTRODUCTION

The material components of high modulus composites are continuing to evolve and their performance characteristics are simultaneously improving. The high strength commercially available carbon fibers such as Celion® have increased in both strength and elongation by approximately 50 percent in the past few years. In addition, with the increasing useage of carbon fiber composites planned for commercial aircraft, step increases in the toughness and environmental resistance of matrix materials are being sought and demonstrated. Still further, a number of efforts are underway to evaluate and assess the effects of fiber finishes on composite performance. The combined result of this development of improved components is seen in the clear-cut emergence of carbon fiber composite systems with significantly improved properties. These component improvements and their resulting effect on composite performance are described herein.

FIBER STRENGTH IMPROVEMENTS

With the rapidly increasing demand for carbon fiber currently being experienced it has been necessary for the leading suppliers to add capacity. These capacity increases have enabled the producers to add new equipment which incorporates their learning experience and has thus allowed evolutionary product improvement to take place. As an example, the improvements for Celion® fiber are shown schematically in Figure 1.

It is important to recognize that these improvements have all taken place without changing the product; as attested to by the retention of constant modulus. Since carbon fiber is a "classical" brittle material, its strength and strain are flaw controlled. It is an understanding of the source of these critical, strength-limiting flaws and corresponding reduction in their size and frequency which have resulted in the demonstrated improvements.

The relationship between fiber and composite properties is shown in Figure 2 where laminate tensile strength is plotted as a function of impregnated strand strength. The impregnated strand is, in fact, a mini-composite composed of one carbon fiber yarn encapsulated in cured epoxy resin. The strand resin used for Figure 2 is a wet system composed largely of Epon 828 and NMA, while the laminates were made with Narmco 5208 resin. It is important to note that reported strand strengths are based solely on fiber cross-sectional areas whereas laminate strengths are given for fiber volumes of 62 percent, a commonly achieved level. Figure 2 also contains a full 100% translation line, i.e., strand strengths versus 62% of strand strength. This translation of strand strength into Narmco 5208 laminate strengths is only 83% effective. There is a resin effect in the translation efficiency which will be illustrated later. It can also be noted that 5208 laminate failure strain is asymptotic to approximately 1.5%, this is a limitation imposed by the resin system.

It should be noted that increases in the fiber tensile strength have been observed to have no effect on the composite compressive, in-plane shear or interlaminar shear strength. These properties are dominated by matrix and fiber-matrix interface properties.

RESIN BEHAVIOR

In addition to the recent increases in carbon fiber strength, developments in resin matrix systems have also led to improved composite properties. In order to isolate fiber and resin dominated composite properties, three resin systems were evaluated in a series of composites made with fibers of varying strengths. The three resins examined were Narmco 5208, Narmco 5245 and Epon 828/NMA. Narmco 5208 is a high modulus, high temperature epoxy resin currently used extensively in the aerospace industry. Narmco 5245 is a new resin system designed to give improved toughness with excellent hot-wet mechanical property retention.

The behavior of 5245 has been previously reported by Hopper and Harrison (1,2). The third resin system investigated is Epon 828/NMA which is a relatively high elongation epoxy. While of experimental interest, the practical application of the system in aerospace composites is limited by poor temperature and moisture resistance. Figure 3 shows the representative tensile stress-strain curves for neat resin castings of these three systems. Table I summarizes the neat resin tensile property data for 5208 and 5245. The important features to note are the lower modulus and increased strength and strain to failure for the 5245 system as compared to 5208. This behavior underlies the increased toughness observed for 5245. The Epon 828/NMA system, as seen in Figure 3, has approximately the same room temperature initial modulus as 5245 with increased strain to failure.

COMPOSITE BEHAVIOR

This study evaluates the composite behavior of systems composed of carbon fibers of varying strengths and the three resin matrices discussed above. It will be shown that certain composite properties are dominated by either the fiber or the matrix while other properties are sensitive to both components.

In Figure 2, it was shown that the unidirectional composite tensile strength is directly related to the fiber strengths with an 83% translation efficiency for the 5208 matrix. Figure 4 shows that the translation efficiency for Narmco's 5245 is approximately 93%. It should also be noted that the 5208 composite tensile failure strain is limited to approximately 1.5%, which is the tensile failure strain of the resin (Figure 3). No such limitation has been observed in 5245 composites. Table II compares the tensile behavior of two Celion® fiber strain variants in composites made with the three resin systems. It can be seen that while the tensile modulus remains constant in each system, the tensile strengths and elongations are strongly dependent on fiber strength as well as the matrix translation efficiency. The best fiber strength translation is observed for the 5245 and 828/NMA resin composites.

Table III summarizes the room temperature composite behavior measured for systems with a variety of fiber elongations ranging from 1.39% to 1.8%. For the properties shown in this table, there was no observed dependence on fiber strength. Thus, the data shown is averaged over the five different data sets obtained with different strength fibers. The resin matrices evaluated were 5208 and 5245. It can be seen that the compressive strength of the 5208 resin composites is higher than that of 5245. This is believed to be due to the higher modulus of 5208 which provides greater lateral support of the fiber and inhibits fiber micro-buckling. For the in-plane shear and transverse tensile results, the higher modulus and lower strength of 5208 as compared to 5245 translates directly into the same relative composite properties. The short beam shear strength, however, is higher for the 5208 resin composite. Note that all of these properties were obtained at room temperature.

IMPACT BEHAVIOR

As stated previously, the tensile behavior of the neat resin castings indicates that Narmco 5245 should have increased toughness as compared to Narmco 5208. Similarly, high strength fibers absorb more energy before they fail and thus should also yield tougher composites. To determine whether these constituent improvements result in improved composite toughness, the impact behavior of these composites was evaluated. To perform these experiments, an instrumented ETI Dynatup 8200 Dart Drop Impact Tester in conjunction with model ETI-300 data processor was employed. This type of test is being used increasingly for evaluating composite impact behavior (3,4). A schematic of the tester is shown in Figure 5. The data is gathered electronically and 1500 data points are computer processed and displayed as shown in the typical output curves of Figure 6. Both force and energy are plotted as a function of deflection. The impact test and laminate variables are listed in Table IV. The force to penetrate a laminate, P_f , was taken as the initial parameter to characterize relative laminate toughness. This parameter was experimentally found to be essentially independent of impact velocity, impact energy and specimen support geometry in the ranges investigated. The value of P_f does vary with indenter diameter and laminate ply sequence so these variables have been fixed at 1.27 cm (0.5 inch) diameter and (45, 90, -45, 0, 45, 90)_s sequence, respectively. The selected impact velocity, impact energy and support geometry for the material characterizations were 2.16 m/sec (7.1 ft/sec), 33.9 J (25 ft-lb), and 6.35 cm (2.5 in.) dia. circular, respectively.

The remaining two parameters are being treated by data normalization using the working curves developed and illustrated in Figures 7 and 8. Figure 7 shows the dependence of P_f on fiber volume for two different resins using a fixed laminate sequence and a constant thickness. Figure 8 depicts the dependence

of P_f on laminate thickness. These data were used to normalize the material characterization data to 60% fiber volume fraction and 0.060 inch thickness.

With this approach the data shown in Figure 9 were obtained. Here the dependence of toughness as characterized by P_f on fiber failure strain and resin are both depicted. As can be seen a 50% increase in fiber strain can result in 50 to 100% increases in toughness, depending upon the resin employed. Similarly there is a relatively constant 100% increase in 5245 laminate toughness over the 5208 property levels. The combined effect of improved fiber strain and the best emerging thermoset resins is a four-fold increase in laminate toughness.

An alternative method of measuring the composite's impact resistance is to subject the laminate to low energy impact and then determine the amount of damage incurred. The low energy impact was obtained by reducing the drop weight and impact velocity such that the indenter rebounded from the specimen surface. The amount of damage resulting from this impact was determined using ultrasonic C-scan evaluations. Figures 10-12 show the ETI-300 force and energy versus deflection output for this low energy impact as well as the C-scan showing the resulting internal damage. This damage is primarily delaminations and trans-ply cracking. As expected, as the impact energy is increased from 0.75 J to 3.17 J, the amount of detectable damage to the sample is increased. To evaluate the low energy impact resistance of various composite systems, specimens are subjected to equivalent low energy impacts and the resulting damage is compared. The results of this study are summarized in Figure 13, where the impact energy causing the damage was 1.50 J. Figure 13a is a C-scan of a 5208 resin composite with fiber failure strain equal to 1.4%. Figure 13b is a C-scan of another 5208 composite with a 1.8% failure strain fiber. The extent of observed damage appears to be the same. Thus, the impact resistance of a composite as measured in this manner appears to be independent of fiber strength. In Figure 13c, the C-scan of a 5245 resin composite with a 1.8% fiber failure strain is shown. The relatively small amount of damage indicates that this composite has increased impact resistance relative to 5208 laminates. Thus, this method of assessing impact resistance supports the improved toughness of the 5245 system seen in the penetration studies.

The two impact test techniques discussed above yield different conclusions on relative material impact resistance. This is due to the different criteria with which impact resistance and composite toughness are assessed. Clearly, much work is needed to define these terms and events more precisely and to develop test techniques which accurately predict in-service behavior. Such tests should include measurements of both the amount of damage incurred during a low energy impact as well as the ability of a material to resist damage propagation when subjected to subsequent end use load conditions.

FIBER-MATRIX INTERFACE EFFECTS

The third component of fiber reinforced composite systems is the fiber-matrix interface. A large contribution to the interface chemistry and physics is determined by the finish applied to the fiber. These finishes on carbon fibers were principally developed as handling aids for fiber weavers and pre-preggers and it is only recently that extensive efforts have been made to improve carbon fiber composite properties via tailoring the interface. A survey of the state-of-the-art was recently published (5). Based on these findings, an experimental program has illustrated that further improvements in impact resistance, P_f , can be achieved. These results are shown in Table V. New finishes A and B show an ability to increase toughness by 30% while maintaining flex and shear strengths. Table VI compares the properties of a standard sized Celion 6000/5208 composite to that of a composite made with 5208 and Celion® with a modified size. In addition to significant improvements in the impact penetration force, slight increases in 0° tensile and flex strengths are also observed. Finish variant C, which is non-bonding, provides even greater toughness but at the loss of flex and shear strengths. The methods

used to characterize wetting and adhesion are, respectively, the Wilhelmy balance (6) and the critical fiber length measurement technique used by Drzal (7). Optimization of the finish may lead to additional increases in composite toughness.

CONCLUSIONS

It has been demonstrated that increases in carbon fiber strength and resin matrix toughness translate into significantly improved composite properties. Specifically, high strength carbon fiber composites have increased unidirectional tensile strengths and increased impact resistance when characterized by the force to penetrate the composite. Resins with increased toughness, such as Narmco's 5245, give improved matrix dominated composite properties, e.g., in-plane shear strength and transverse tensile strength. In addition, significant improvements in impact behavior as measured both by penetration force and low energy impact damage are seen with 5245 resin composites. This new resin also provides significantly improved hot-wet performance in comparison with conventionally toughened systems, e.g., rubber modified epoxies.

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Figure 1

Figure 2

Figure 3

Figure 4

Figure 5

Figure 6

Figure 7

Figure 8

Figure 9

Figure 10

Figure 11

Figure 12

ULTRASONIC C-SCANS SHOWING LOW ENERGY IMPACT DAMAGE

a) 5205/1.4% FIBER STRAIN

b) 5208/1.8% FIBER STRAIN

c) 5245/1.4% FIBER STRAIN

Figure 13

CAST RESIN TENSILE PROPERTIES (RT)

	5245	5208	828/NMA
STRENGTH, ksi (MPa)	10.1 (69.9)	7.3 (50.3)	9.0 (62.0)
MODULUS, ksi (GPa)	483 (3.33)	561 (3.87)	500 (3.45)
ELONGATION, %	213	ca. 1.5	3.5

Table I

UNIDIRECTIONAL TENSILE PROPERTIES

	STANDARD CELCON [®] FIBER	COMPOSITE PROPERTIES		
		5208	5245	828 NMA
STANDARD CELCON [®] FIBER		COMPOSITE PROPERTIES		
	STAND. PROPERTIES x .62	5208	5245	828 NMA
STRENGTH (GPa)	2.01	1.65	2.00	1.92
MODULUS (GPa)	147	148	143	145
STRAIN TO FAILURE, %	1.39	1.14	1.40	1.34
HIGH STRENGTH CELCON [®] FIBER		COMPOSITE PROPERTIES		
	STAND. PROPERTIES x .62	5208	5245	828 NMA
STRENGTH (GPa)	2.63	2.03	2.52	2.43
MODULUS (GPa)	147	148	147	150
STRAIN TO FAILURE, %	1.80	1.34	1.72	1.62

Table II

COMPOSITE PROPERTY COMPARISON (RT)

(DATA AVERAGED OVER FIVE COMPOSITE SYSTEMS WITH VARYING FIBER STRENGTH)

	MATRIX MATERIALS	
	5245	5208
COMPRESSION (0°) (ASTM D-3410)		
STRENGTH, ksi (GPa)	185 (1.27)	211 (1.45)
MODULUS, msi (GPa)	16.8 (1.16)	17.4 (1.20)
IN-PLANE SHEAR (ASTM D-351B)		
STRENGTH, ksi (GPa)	15.8 (10.9)	12.7 (87.5)
MODULUS, ksi (GPa)	722 (4.97)	769 (5.30)
TRANSVERSE TENSION (ASTM D-3039)		
STRENGTH, ksi (MPa)	10.2 (70.3)	7.85 (54.1)
MODULUS, msi (GPa)	1.31 (9.03)	1.38 (9.51)
SHORT BEAM SHEAR		
STRENGTH, ksi (MPa)	16.2 (112)	18.3 (126)

Table III

IMPACT TEST VARIABLES

IMPACT VELOCITY ($V = \sqrt{2gh}$)
 AVAILABLE ENERGY AT IMPACT ($E = mgh$)
 SPECIMEN SUPPORT GEOMETRY
 INDENTER DIAMETER

COMPOSITE LAMINATE CONSTRUCTION VARIABLES

THICKNESS (NUMBER OF PLYS)
 FIBER VOLUME FRACTION
 FIBER ORIENTATIONS (STACKING SEQUENCE)

Table VI

EFFECTS OF INTERFACE ON CELCON COMPOSITE PERFORMANCE (DEVELOPMENTAL EPOXY MATRIX)

FIBER-FINISH VARIANT	EQUILIBRIUM WETTING FORCE (g)	SINGLE FILAMENT SHEAR (MPa)	SHORT BEAM SHEAR STRENGTH (MPa)	0° FLEX STRENGTH (MPa)	IMPACT RESISTANCE P _g (N)
CONTROL	91	76.5	95.8	1850	1482
A	127	63.4	86.8	2090	1927
B	82	64.1	90.9	1930	1838
C	51	16.5	34.5	810	2221

Table V

EVALUATION OF CELCON 6000 FINISH VARIANT

PROPERTY	TEST TEMP. (°C)	SAMPLE		
		STANDARD	MODIFIED	
IMPACT, P _g (N)	RT	1350	1740	
	TENSILE	STR. (GPa)	1.67	1.83
		MOD. (GPa)	140	142
		STR. (GPa)	1.74	1.81
0° FLEX	WET STR. (GPa)	MOD. (GPa)	154	153
		STR. (GPa)	1.74	1.78
	MOD. (GPa)	STR. (GPa)	1.97	2.04
		MOD. (GPa)	119	121
90° FLEX	WET STR. (GPa)	STR. (GPa)	1.72	1.88
		MOD. (GPa)	119	119
	STR. (MPa)	STR. (MPa)	1.07	0.87
		MOD. (MPa)	132	112
±45° TENSION	WET STR. (MPa)	STR. (MPa)	79.2	80.6
		MOD. (MPa)	53.7	48.9
	STR. (MPa)	STR. (MPa)	87.5	82.7
		MOD. (MPa)	9.03	9.03
0° COMPRESSION	WET STR. (MPa)	STR. (MPa)	63.4	56.5
		MOD. (MPa)	31.0	26.9
	STR. (MPa)	STR. (MPa)	161	159
		MOD. (MPa)	4.75	4.34
0° COMPRESSION	WET STR. (MPa)	STR. (MPa)	145	132
		MOD. (MPa)	3.72	3.24
	STR. (GPa)	STR. (GPa)	129	112
		MOD. (GPa)	2.69	2.27
MOD.	STR. (GPa)	1.55	1.52	
	MOD.	119	119	

Table IV